

Thermal Decomposition of Some Sulphates and Monofluophosphates

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Thermal decomposition of the hydrates of cadmium, manganese, nickel, chromium (iii) and iron (iii) sulphates and corresponding monofluophosphates were studied with the help of Chevenard and Stanton thermo balances. The rate of heating was maintained at 240° per hour.

All the sulphates under investigation were recrystallised from the AnalR samples. The cadmium and manganese sulphates were crystallised by the method of spontaneous crystallisation. Chromium sulphate was recrystallised by the method suggested by Schroter¹. Ferric sulphate hydrate was prepared by adding calculated amount of sulphuric acid and hydrogen peroxide to ferrous sulphate solution until it ceased to give blue precipitate with potassium ferricyanide². Monofluophosphates were prepared as suggested in our previous work³.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pyrolysis curves obtained are shown and discussed below.

CdSO₄ 8/3H₂O. The curve indicates that CdSO₄ 8/3H₂O starts losing water molecules at about of 110° and 5/3 molecules of water were lost completely at about 140°. The monohydrate CdSO₄H₂O left is stable from 140° to 200°. Again the decomposition starts and

1. Schroter, J. W. Mellor, Comprehensive treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry, 1962, Vol. XI, p. 435., Longmans.
2. Mellor and Perkin, Inorganic Chemistry, p. 863.
3. E. B. Singh and P. C. Sinha, Jour. Indian Chem. Soc., 1964, 41, 407.

the last molecule of water is lost at about 230° after which there is no change up to 700°. The residue left at this stage was analysed and was found to contain Cd : 53.7%; SO₄ : 46.2% which corresponds to anhydrous cadmium sulphate. The three horizontals in the curve correspond to CdSO₄·8/3H₂O, CdSO₄·H₂O and CdSO₄. Our result differs respect of temperature from the result obtained by the coworker of Duval⁴.

MnSO₄·4H₂O. Manganese sulphate tetra hydrate is not stable at the initial temperature of the furnace. A horizontal stretch is witnessed between 90° and 315° which corresponds to monohydrate. Above 315° decomposition again starts and at 345° dehydration seems to be complete and a new horizontal level corresponding to anhydrous salt is observed which was supported by analytical result : Mn : 36.3%; SO₄ : 63.8%. The anhydrous salt does not show any sign of decomposition up to 700°. This result also differs from the data mentioned in Duval's book⁵ as far as temperature is concerned.

NiSO₄·7H₂O. Hepta hydrate is not stable at the initial temp. of the furnace as it loses one molecule of water at about 30° giving hexa hydrate. Hexa hydrate is stable up to 60° as indicated by the horizontal stretch in the T.G. curve. After 60° it starts losing

water molecules rapidly and continuously up to 200°. Thereafter the rate of loss becomes slow but continuous and finally anhydrous salt (yellow) is obtained which remains stable

4. C. Duval, Inorganic Thermogravimetric Analysis, 2nd Edn., 1962, p. 358, Elsevier Publishing Co.
5. C. Duval, Inorganic Thermogravimetric Analysis, 2nd Edn., 1962, p. 187, Elsevier Publishing Co.

between 450° and 700°. The analysis of the salt at this stage corresponds to anhydrous nickel sulphate. Ni : 37.9%; SO₄ : 62.15%. The T.G. curve shows that nickel sulphate forms no stable hydrate below the hexa hydrate. The stretch in the curve between 270° and 350° is not perfectly horizontal and suggests the absence of any definite stable stage.

Cr₂(SO₄)₃18H₂O. The pyrolysis curve in this case is interesting. Actually no horizontal level is observed except between 300° and 650°. This corresponds to the anhydrous salt : Cr : 26.4%; SO₄ : 73.3%. It starts decomposing into chromic oxide and sulphur dioxide after 650°. From the curve it appears that the hydrate loses water up to 300° but the loss is not uniform and breaks in the curve at about 100°, 160°, and 220° are noticed. The breaks correspond to Cr₂(SO₄)₃ 12H₂O and Cr₂(SO₄)₃6H₂O respectively. As Cr₂(SO₄)₃18H₂O loses water molecules at room temperature, that salt had already lost some water molecules at the starting temperature of the furnace. The curve does not give evidence of any stable hydrate after 52°. The above hydrates may be taken as stable for a very short range of temperature, but the range is too small to support the stability of the two hydrates.

Fe₂(SO₄)₃9H₂O. Most of the water molecules are lost at room temperature and from 50° a continuous dehydration is observed up to 250°. After it a horizontal stretch is noticed corresponding to anhydrous salt which is stable up to 610°. (Fe : 27.8%; SO₄ : 72%). Above it, it decomposes into its oxide and sulphur dioxide. The curve does not indicate the existence of any definite stable hydrate of ferric sulphate above 50°.

CdPO₃F8/3H₂O. It is stable up to 180°. Thereafter decomposition starts and is rapid between 250° and 525°. Above 750° no further loss is observed.

MnPO₃F2H₂O. The compound is stable up to 260° after which it starts losing weight continuously up to 950°.

NiPO₃F6H₂O. The hydrate is stable up to 375° after which the decomposition is rapid and continuous up to 825°.

Cr₂(PO₃F)₃18H₂O. The curve indicates that the loss is continuous up to 900°.

Fe₂(PO₃F)₃12H₂O. From 150° the decomposition starts and loss is continuous up to 760°.

The pyrolysis curves of all monofluophosphates are not so simple and clear cut as in the case of sulphates. They are practically of the same nature and the decomposition may be due to the reactions taking place as suggested by Kinh⁶.

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